

**PROFESSIONAL TEACHING
COMPETENCES FOR CLIL TEACHERS:
A PROPOSAL OF THE KEY
PRINCIPLES**

Linguistics

Keywords: CLIL, competences, principles, integration, teacher.

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Abstract

This work has been carried out in parallel with the doctoral research that I have carried out on the necessary professional competencies of a CLIL professor developed in the field of education, at the University of La Laguna. The aim of the research was to define and study the professional teaching competences required for a CLIL teacher in the current context of compulsory secondary education. This paper aims to show a proposal on what principles are necessary in the training of the CLIL teacher. First, the three proposed principles will be set out and presented: the principle of integration which understands language, content and culture as closely related elements, the principle of updating, with particular emphasis on the continuing training to be acquired and renewed by teachers in a lifelong learning process, and finally, the principle of simultaneity according to which the educator must implement different professional skills and competences in a synchronised manner. Secondly, a brief introduction will be made to set a precedent for the creation and rationale of these principles. Third, definitions and descriptions will be provided to clarify exactly what these organisational principles are, which aim to regulate the competencies and skills that CLIL teachers must possess or acquire. Finally, the conclusions of the study on these principles and the necessity of this proposal will be presented.

Introduction

Nowadays, social, political, economic, educational changes have motivated that the way of learning and communicating has been updated and, in this way, the way of teaching must also be adapted by integrating elements and tools, which are useful in daily life and for the students' future. The changes in education are visible from the school, this is not limited to being a simple place where you can learn procedures and concepts but is understood, according to Echavarría (2003: 4), as “a space for interaction, construction and development of potentialities necessary for the understanding of the world, its relationships and its possible transformations” that will be fundamental for the personal, academic and professional learners development.

In addition, we must bear in mind that the changes that occur in education are also reflected in work activity and vice versa. New professional profiles that are demanded in the labor market are constantly created and, in turn, other professions that are overcome by the moment we live, as a result of the evolution and transformation of our society disappear. For this reason, uncertainty is present in the professional and educational world. “The professionals of tomorrow should be more versatile and know how to take advantage of changing circumstances, anticipate the new needs that will arise throughout a long professional career” (Manso and Moya, 2019: 31). We must consider this factor and educate students with useful tools for their lives, regardless of the profession or work they are dedicated to, but the skills they possess.

Based on the new paradigms of changes in education, the CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning) approach can be described as “flexible and can be adapted to different

contexts, nonetheless, for the approach to be justifiable and sustainable, its theoretical basis must be rigorous and transparent in practice” (Coyle, Hood and Marsh, 2010: 1). This learning provides a more natural and updated view in the use of foreign languages, because languages are considered a communicative element and not only curricular content. The learning that is carried out through CLIL education encourages the acquisition and improvement of the foreign language that is used as a means of communication and, at the same time, achieves cognitive learning objectives in terms of curricular content.

Multilingual education is necessary to prepare students for the needs of the workplace, so CLIL education tries to facilitate language learning in a natural context contextualized with the use that is being given. Therefore, this type of education facilitates the inclusion of curricular content in conjunction with foreign languages, through the implementation of participatory and active methodologies that are adapted to the needs of the classroom. Being the student protagonist of his own teaching-learning process can not conceive of traditional methodologies, but methodologies that provide opportunities for students to put their knowledge and experiences into practice.

So, it is necessary to consider the formative aspect of CLIL teachers as an essential tool in the acquisition and improvement of their professional skills. It is important to organize what are the specific professional competences of CLIL teachers, to promote a homogeneous teacher training consistent with the educational regulations, the context and the reality that we live. This document reflects the previous literature about CLIL education and competences makes report to the instruments and data obtained in my own doctoral thesis (Mallorquín, 2019) and a series of principles, which have been proposed to organize the competences. The aim of this research is to propose the principles that expect to be the axis on which the competences of a CLIL educator (secondary school) are organized, due to the lack of a structure.

The professional teaching competences

The professional competences of a CLIL teacher must be on the one hand, general and shared with the rest of the teachers, since it is necessary to have a common base, and on the other hand, it is absolutely essential to establish professional competences that are specific of the CLIL teachers.

Firstly, based on literature and theoretical bases, a questionnaire is prepared for CLIL teachers of the Secondary education of the island of Tenerife and also for university teachers who are nationwide experts in CLIL education.

This questionnaire consists of 10 questions: questions ranging from 1-3 are closed questions with unique answer selection and deal with aspects related to know the participants. Question number 4 is a closed type multiple answer option, if they considered it is necessary they have a space to add the information they want to contribute. This question was aimed at knowing what skills currently have these teachers. The questions ranging from number 5 to 8 are, again,

closed-type questions with a single answer, although as in question number 4, if the participants consider necessary, they could add information in a space reserved for it. These questions are based on levels of understanding in foreign language and training provided by the Ministry of Education, Universities, Culture and Sports of the Autonomous Community of the Canary Islands. In question number 9, a series of competencies related to educational literature and pedagogical elements of the teaching profession are proposed, so that the participants in this study could, through multiple selection, choose the competencies they believe necessary for CLIL teachers, in addition they are given the possibility of adding any competence that they consider relevant. Finally, issue number 10 deals with the professional teaching competences proposed in the previous question (9) in gradation scale format (always, often, sometimes, never) to get their opinion about how often these professional competences are put into practice. Below, there is an image (figure 1) of a filled questionnaire by CLIL Secondary teachers and university experts.

Figure 1: an example of questionnaire

Docentes o profesionales relacionados con la enseñanza CLIL/AICLE. Universidad de La Laguna

Cuestionario sobre Educación CLIL/AICLE.

Este estudio se lleva a cabo dentro de un programa de Doctorado de Educación, en la línea de investigación "Enseñanza y aprendizaje en áreas de Lenguas Extranjeras: Inglés" de la Universidad de La Laguna. En relación con este estudio, nos gustaría que completase el cuestionario siguiendo las instrucciones. La información que nos proporcione será confidencial, solamente las personas autorizadas a este estudio podrán manejarla. Le agradecemos de antemano la información brindada.

Instrucciones: Seleccione solamente una respuesta a cada pregunta.

1. Género.
 Masculino. Femenino.

2. Grupo de edad.
 < 34 51-60
 35-40 > 60
 41-50

3. ¿Cuántos años lleva profesionalmente relacionado con la impartición del CLIL/AICLE?
 <1 11-15
 1-4 > 20
 5-10

4. Seleccione cuáles de los siguientes títulos está en posesión.
 Licenciado. Máster de formación del profesorado.
 Graduado. Curso habilitador CLIL/AICLE.
 Nativo en la lengua extranjera. Certificado idiomas.
 CAP. Otros:

5. Seleccione el nivel de idiomas que tiene acreditado.
 A1 C1
 A2 C2
 B1 Otros:
 B2

6. ¿Ha realizado algún curso acreditador de docente CLIL/AICLE?
 Sí. ¿Cuál? _____ No.

7. ¿La Consejería de Educación les facilita la actualización y reciclaje de conocimiento sobre CLIL?
 Sí. No.

8. Se siente satisfecho con la formación proporcionada por la Consejería de Educación?
 Sí. ¿Por qué? _____ No. ¿Por qué? _____

Docentes o profesionales relacionados con la enseñanza CLIL/AICLE. Universidad de La Laguna

9. ¿Qué competencias profesionales creen que son necesarias para los docentes CLIL?

<input type="checkbox"/> Nivel de idiomas. <input type="checkbox"/> Licenciatura o graduado. <input type="checkbox"/> CAP o Máster de formación del profesorado. <input type="checkbox"/> Programar o planificar situaciones de aprendizaje. <input type="checkbox"/> Aplicar diversas metodologías activas y participativas. <input type="checkbox"/> Aplicar diversos tipos de evaluación.	<input type="checkbox"/> Contextualización de las situaciones de aprendizaje. <input type="checkbox"/> Dominio del CLIL. <input type="checkbox"/> El doble rol del docente como profesor y como investigador. <input type="checkbox"/> Motivación del trabajo en grupos cooperativos. <input type="checkbox"/> Otras:
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10. ¿A qué nivel sugiere que las competencias anteriores sean puestas en práctica. (Marque con una X).

	Siempre	Con frecuencia	A veces	Nunca
1. Nivel de idiomas.				
2. Licenciatura o graduado.				
3. CAP o Máster de formación del profesorado.				
4. Programar o planificar situaciones de aprendizaje.				
5. Aplicar diversas metodologías activas y participativas.				
6. Aplicar diversos tipos de evaluación.				
7. Contextualización de las situaciones de aprendizaje.				
8. Dominio del CLIL.				
9. El doble rol del docente como profesor y como investigador.				
10. Motivación del trabajo en grupos cooperativos.				
11. Otros:				

Aim of the principles

Professional skills and competences are important in themselves. However, the way in which the organizational axis has been drawn is key to understand the composition of the profile of a CLIL Secondary education teacher. The professional competences of a CLIL teacher extracted from the research questionnaires will be organized according to three principles: the principle of integration, the principle of updating and the principle of simultaneity, these characteristics are main parts of CLIL teaching.

Principle of integration

The principle of integration is understood as the way in which a series of teaching skills are structured and work together to favor the development of students significant learning. This principle includes linguistic competence and curricular content that are essential factors in CLIL teaching and work together with the third element that will be culture. According to the extraction of research data, language is considered a relevant professional teaching competence in this type of teaching, since it will be the way in which the contents are acquired, understood and communicated.

Table number 1. Foreign language

<i>Foreign language</i>			
		Frequency	Percentage
Acceptable	Affirmative	23	100,0
	Total	23	100,0

The foreign language will be the linguistic element acting as vehicular, which will allow the teacher to communicate effectively. This does not only mean that the teacher is able to speak or write properly in English or any other language, but is able to facilitate the acquisition of knowledge through the use of this language. The teacher must have linguistic tools that allow him to bring the knowledge to the students without the foreign language itself being an impediment, but to consider the English language what it is, a language, a form of communication to be able to take it to the classroom naturally. Therefore, applying this type of teaching using a foreign language will allow students to learn, acquire, improve, experience conflicts and learn to resolve them as they have done in learning knowledge using their mother tongue.

It is also important to consider cultural aspects as part of the natural learning of the foreign language. The students carried out a questionnaire giving their opinion about the CLIL project or program of their educational center and paying attention to the cultural aspects of the foreign language. This factor is essential to develop a contextualized teaching. It is positive that from the schools the cultural component is promoted, beyond the traditional festivities, because it is a knowledge as enriching as the language itself and will provide more contextualized learning.

Table number 2. Cultural activities different from Halloween, Christmas, Easter...

<i>Cultural activities different from Halloween, Christmas, Easter...</i>			
		Frequency	Percentage
Acceptable	Affirmative	222	58,3
	Negative	159	41,7
	Total	381	100,0

Principle of updating

The professional teaching competences that are necessary for a CLIL teacher in Secondary Education, according to the research that has been developed. The second principle is proposed through which these professional skills are organized and structured. As previously described in relation to the inclusion of culture in the principle of integration, contextualization is essential to give meaning to the classroom learning situations. However, it is necessary to deepen this aspect by covering other professional teaching competencies.

The updating principle is proposed as the idea that professional teaching competences must be mutable, flexible, contextualized and current to create meaningful learning for students. Education is in a process of continuous transformation and today, every day in a classroom is far from traditional education. Currently, it seeks to achieve a contextualized, motivating, active education that allows students to learn in a consistent manner with the world in which they live.

In the first stage of learning, teachers acquire an initial training, in which they are trained in knowledge, methodologies, educational regulations, etc; which will allow them to sketch a first drawing about their future educational experiences. In his professional career, the teacher who already has an initial learning will continue his permanent training that will allow him to update and adapt to different methodologies, materials, perform contextualized learning situations, learn and apply different types of assessment, as well as use programs or technological applications that are beneficial and provide learning opportunities to students and teachers.

This updating principle includes an essential competence that is, the ability of the teacher to renew their own professional skills continuously. According to the data obtained in the research questionnaires, training is an absolutely essential tool for teachers. As shown in the table below, teachers believe that CLIL education training is essential. In this way, CLIL teachers will be continuously training to adapt to new realities and offer a more up-to-date education.

Table number 3. Command of CLIL

<i>Command of CLIL</i>			
		Frequency	Percentage
Acceptable	Affirmative	17	73,9
	Negative	6	26,1
	Total	23	100,0

Moreover, another essential aspect in terms of teacher training is the methodology. CLIL education is committed to bring active and participatory methodologies to the classroom that promote active student learning as protagonists, putting their knowledge into practice, learning from their mistakes and taking them as part of their learning process. So it is essential that teachers are in continuous methodological training to adapt themselves to the students different ways of learning.

Table number 4. Active and participatory methodologies

<i>Active and participatory methodologies</i>			
		Frequency	Percentage
Acceptable	Affirmative	18	78,3
	Negative	5	21,7
	Total	23	100,0

Principle of simultaneity

The principle of simultaneity is understood as the principle that integrates the professional competences of a specialized teacher in CLIL teaching synchronously. The skills of CLIL professionals will provide significance in the students learning process, if it is carried out considering this principle.

The fundamental aspects that are integrated into CLIL teaching are necessary to describe the principle of simultaneity, this occurs because this principle seeks that these essential elements take part in the teaching synchronously. In the first place, the foreign language, as is already known, is an essential component of CLIL education, however, it has no place if it is not carried out as a contextualized and integrated part of the hand of the curricular contents of the educational stage of Secondary Education. The language must be introduced simultaneously with students' knowledge, as an integrated part of the lessons. Likewise, the curricular content must be worked together, in the first place, with the foreign language and thus create schemes of knowledge for students that are built from the simultaneity of the contents and the language in a natural way, considering the language as a communicative element that will allow us to access, learn, teach and

develop knowledge. In this way, the elements of CLIL education will not be considered as isolated aspects that make up this type of teaching, but rather the teacher will try to include these elements in an integrated and simultaneous way, so that a path in the teaching is carried out -coherent and natural student learning. As in the classroom with traditional methodologies and using the mother tongue as a vehicular language, curricular contents are taught using the language simultaneously, TAC, values and key competencies; CLIL education seeks to achieve this same synchronization using the foreign language as a communicative vehicle and a series of specific skills to this type of teaching.

Conclusion

The three principles proposed are: the integration principle, the update principle and the simultaneity principle. The principle of integration aims to be the integrating competence element of the linguistic, contitudinal and cultural skills of the CLIL teacher.

It has been proposed as a necessary catalyst tool that allows to regulate the professional teaching competences, which facilitate the acquisition of knowledge and the competence learning to learn. Second, the update principle aims to apply flexibility and mutability to the professional competences of CLIL teachers. Teachers need to update their training permanently in methodologies, in the domain of CLIL, perform training in TAC, level of foreign languages, diverse ways to assess, adapt to the students difficulties and ways of learning. Furthermore, it is also necessary to program and plan in CLIL teaching, with the complexity and effort that it requires, since it is not a question of making a translation of the traditional classes, but this type of teaching requires a contextualization and own elements that make this type of education consistent. And it is also necessary to promote the double role of the teacher that will allow him to improve his own professional practice by carrying out his own self-evaluation and considering the aspects that the students consider necessary to revise or adapt of our teaching exercise. By means of the own investigation the improvement of the professional practice and the curiosity to include or adapt new acquired elements and to realize tester in the classroom is promoted. Without this principle of updating, CLIL teaching would be retaking traditional models of teaching lessons in the classroom, since it would not be motivating the learning of skills and tools that are useful, effective and close to the reality that surrounds learners.

Finally, the principle of simultaneity aims to achieve the integration of CLIL professional teaching competences simultaneously. This principle aims to create an atmosphere of integration of elements in student learning. It is based on the results obtained in the research of the doctoral thesis (Mallorquín, 2019), in which the opinions of the participating teachers in the study about the professional competences that they consider necessary for a CLIL professor. It should be especially emphasized that this principle aims to motivate teachers to use various active and participatory methodologies, in addition, to apply different types of assessment and motivate the double role of the teacher as an educator and as a researcher. Educating students in values of

autonomy, critical and reflective thinking and promoting respect and tolerance, since they are basic values for living in society.

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